

Performance of broadcast seeded TM8089

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TM8089 is a high-yielding blast-tolerant red rice selection from TKM9. It was isolated at the Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur, to replace highly blast-susceptible TKM9. We compared TM8089, which is suitable for rainfed lowland cultivation, and TKM9 broadcast seeded and transplanted in 200-m² observational plots.

Broadcast seeding was at 100 kg seed/ha. Transplanting was at 60 kg seed/ha. Thinning and gap filling were done in the broadcast plots; transplanting was at 2 to 3

Comparison of TM8089 and TKM9 broadcast and transplanted.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Character	Broadcast seeding			Transplanting	
	TKM9	TM8089	TKM9	TKM9	TM8089
Plant height (cm)	93.8	95.2	99.0	(5.696)**	103.6
Productive tillers	5.0	5.0	10.4	(4.472)**	10.6
Panicle length (cm)	20.6	(1.963)**	18.6	(6.321)**	22.4
Panicle weight (g)	3.0	3.0	3.0	(8.179)**	3.2
Grains/panicle	71.0	(2.855)**	76.0	(4.989)**	97.0
Yield (t/ha)	2.6	3.1	5.0		5.2
Difference (%)	-	17.5	-		5.5

^at values in parentheses are highly significant.

seedlings/hill, 15- × 10-cm spacing. Management practices were common for both planting treatments.

Twenty hills were selected at random from each plot and plant height, productive tillers, panicle length, panicle weight, and grains/panicle were recorded. Differences between direct seeding and transplanting were distinct

(see table). All traits were lower under broadcast seeding, in particular, number of productive tillers.

TM8089 was better than TKM9 in all traits except panicle length. Its higher yield is attributed to more grains per panicle under broadcast seeding and to more grains per panicle and higher panicle weight under transplanting. □

Cross compatibility between Guizhou traditional upland sinica varieties and short-statured indica varieties

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Cross compatibility between 296 Guizhou traditional upland sinica varieties and 3 short-statured indica varieties was tested in 663 F₁ combinations in 1985.

A number of the local upland sinicas have high cross compatibility with short-statured indicas. The upland sinicas have higher cross compatibility with the short-statured indicas than with lowland sinicas (Table 1). They also have distinctly higher cross compatibility with short-statured Guichao 2 than with common short-statured sinicas (Table 2). The high and low cross compatibility between sinicas and indicas are negatively correlated with the latitudes and elevations of the origins of the sinicas and positively with mean temperature and >10 °C cumulative 1-yr temperature of the places of origin. The closest relationship is with latitude. □

Table 1. Distribution of cross compatibility (CC) between Guizhou upland sinica varieties and short-statured indica varieties. China, 1985.

Male parent	Total (no.)	>50% CC		>60% CC		>70% CC		>80% CC		>90% CC	
		no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%
Lowland rice	545	294	53.94	151	27.71	55	10.09	11	2.02		
Upland rice	118	81	68.64	45	33.14	22	18.64	9	7.63	3	2.5
Total	663	375	56.56	196	29.26	77	11.61	20	3.02	3	0.45

Table 2. CC of short-statured Guichao 2 with local upland sinica and common short-statured sinica rice varieties.

Male parent	F ₁ distribution (no.)			F ₁ CC		
	Total	> 60% CC	170% CC	Highest	Lowest	Mean
Local upland sinica	22	2	1	72.52	30.63	49.90
Common short-statured sinica	24	0	0	50.36	10.87	33.69

Varieties suitable for direct seeding in the Ganges floodplain

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The Ganges River floodplain, formed through soil erosion and deposits, is estimated to total 0.24 million ha. The land is subjected to periodical flooding

in the wet season and crops are generally grown in the winter season.

With the introduction of bamboo boring, another crop in the stabilized floodplain in the summer season before flooding has become possible.

As a short-duration summer rice crop after winter crop harvest, transplanted, irrigated Pusa 2-21 and Pusa 33 performed well and were harvested before flooding started. But summer rice

in these areas is not catching on because of the costs of transplanting and irrigating. An early-maturing rice variety khat could be direct seeded and grown with limited irrigation is desirable.

We evaluated the performance of 11 early-maturing rice varieties under direct seeding with limited irrigation in Ziauddinpur floodplain. The trial was in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. Seeds at 80 kg/ha were sown 10 May 1985 in rows 15 cm apart. Fertilizer at 80-17.5-20 kg NPK/ha was applied. One presowing irrigation and two irrigations during the dry spell were given. The crop received 64 mm rainfall in 7 d in May, 222 mm in 18 d in Jun, and 387 mm in 23 d in Jul.

Pusa 2-21 and Hathi Jhulan failed because of a severe attack of brown leaf spot disease. Varieties ES1-1-1,

Plant height, days to heading, grain yield, and yield attributes of 9 direct-seeded varieties, Bihar, India, summer 1985.

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% heading	Panicles/m ²	Panicle length (cm)	Total spikelets/panicle	Filled spikelets/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET6148	85.2	98	129	18.4	64.3	47.0	21.6	0.9
ES1-1-1	86.0	66	122	14.4	68.2	58.5	18.7	1.2
ES1-2-3	78.7	66	144	15.1	66.1	56.5	18.2	1.5
IET7617	82.2	91	127	18.4	63.0	46.1	21.3	0.9
IET7564	96.2	66	135	21.3	118.3	100.3	20.0	2.1
IET7613	91.3	92	124	18.9	65.8	48.6	22.0	0.8
ES21-2-1	81.2	85	116	14.5	65.7	51.3	19.0	1.0
Cauvery	84.3	86	117	18.8	74.2	54.6	20.9	1.0
Pusa 33	88.3	98	114	18.1	74.9	56.3	21.4	1.1
CD (0.05)	6.7		14	1.4	6.9	6.0	1.0	0.6

ES1-2-3, and IET7564 were the earliest to reach 50% heading, 66 d after sowing (see table). Heading time in general was 15-20 d longer than in wet season, perhaps because of soil moisture stress during early crop stages.

IET7564 had significantly higher

grain yield because it had more panicles/m² and filled spikelets/panicle. This semitall variety develops sufficient foliage in early stages to smother weeds. It has good grain quality and matures within 90 d, for harvest before floods in early Aug. □

Evapotranspiration rates of Jaya and Triveni varieties

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We studied evapotranspiration (ET) of Jaya (120 d) and Triveni (105 d) based on data collected 1978-85 at RARS, Pattambi (10°48'N, 76°12'E). ET was measured using two sets of volumetric lysimeters, and potential ET (PET) was computed using the Blaney-Criddle formula as modified by Doorenbos and Pruitt. Soil was lateritic sandy loam.

The varieties were not observed simultaneously, but were compared on the basis of daily mean ET in relation to

Table 2. Growth parameters of Triveni and Jaya, Kerala, India, 1986 kharif.

	Leaf area index	Leaf width (mm)	Leaf angle ^a
	<i>70 d after sowing^b</i>		
Jaya	4.0 ^d	8.0 ^e	170 ^{od}
Triveni	6.3	7.5	18°
	<i>Flowering phase^c</i>		
Jaya	4.2 ^e	8.9 ^d	16 ^{od}
Triveni	4.7	7.7	18°

^a70 d after sowing and 10 d after flowering.

^bTriveni and Jaya were sown on the same day.

^cAv of 3 stages; 1 wk before flowering, at flowering, and 10 d after flowering. ^dSignificant at the 1% level. ^eNot significant.

Table 1. Varietal variation in ET rates in relation to average PET. Kerala, India, 1986 kharif and rabi.

Variety	Kharif			Rabi		
	ET (mm/d)	PET (mm/d)	Percent increase of ET over PET	ET (mm/d)	PET (mm/d)	Percent increase of ET over PET
Jaya ^a	4.95	3.51	41	6.05	4.15	46
Triveni ^b	4.90	3.47	41	6.19	3.93	58
Difference in ET rates in relation to av PET	+0.05			-0.14		

^aAv of 3 seasons for kharif and 2 for rabi. ^bAv of 5 seasons each for kharif and rabi.

average evaporative demand of the atmosphere.

ET of Jaya was 41% higher than PET in Jun-Sep (kharif) and 46% higher in Oct-Jan (rabi). ET of Triveni was 41% higher than PET in Jun-Sep and 58% higher in Oct-Jan (Table 1). Jaya and Triveni had similar ET during kharif, but Triveni used 0.14 mm/d more water than Jaya during rabi. The higher ET of Triveni during rabi may have been because it had higher leaf area index and leaf angle and smaller leaf width than Jaya (Table 2). □

Rice grain dormancy and its alleviation

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Seeds of IR8, Jaya, PR106, PR4141, Basmati 370, and Punjab Basmati I were collected immediately after harvest, dried to 12% moisture, and kept under ambient conditions in cloth bags. We began germination tests immediately after harvest, then every 7 d until seeds